

Language Data Commons of Australia Co-design Workshop Report for the HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons

The Australian Research Data Commons

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

From 2022, the ARDC has been making a major investment in digital research infrastructure for humanities, arts, social sciences and Indigenous research data communities. This work has been done in accordance with the 2016 NCRIS Roadmap and Department of Education commissioned studies. The projects undertaken in this area formed an emerging *HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons*.

In late 2023, the ARDC received the largest ever investment in HASS and Indigenous Research Capability. In Early 2024 we initiated a process of co-design to deliver on an expanded HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons, covering existing and new areas of research infrastructure.

The *Language Data Commons of Australia* tackles the challenges researchers face in accessing and utilising language data for research. It aims to support researchers to deliver innovative research outcomes, and opens up the social and economic possibilities of Australia's language data for translational research in the national interest.

The ARDC is co-designing its new infrastructure investments with the research community and other stakeholders to ensure that we create the greatest possible impact. Development of this infrastructure follows the [HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework](#).

The ARDC conducted two co-design workshops in February-March 2024 to shape plans for this investment opportunity. These workshops were open to all, and were attended by a total of 48 participants from 25 organisations, including Australian and international universities, GLAM organisations and research infrastructure providers. In Workshop 1 we refined our understanding of the challenge to be addressed and found out what outcomes participants hoped to see. In Workshop 2 we explored how the desired outcomes could be achieved within the new infrastructure investment, and discussed requirements and practical considerations for the potential solutions.

THE HASS AND INDIGENOUS RESEARCH DATA COMMONS

The ARDC is planning major investment in digital research infrastructure for humanities, arts, social sciences and Indigenous research data communities.

The 2016 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap identified avenues to enhance the impact of HASS (Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences) and Indigenous research, proposing improvements in coordinating research infrastructure to facilitate access to and analysis of physical and digital collections. These improvements involve leveraging tools like digitization, aggregation, and interpretation platforms.

Subsequently, the Australian Government Department of Education commissioned three studies to pinpoint investment-ready programs eligible for National Research Infrastructure funding. While not all recommendations from these studies received funding initially, the identified activities demonstrated a high level of readiness to engage with and benefit from the development of a [HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons](#) (RDC).

From 2022-2024 the ARDC-led HASS and Indigenous RDC has implemented a number of these activities, including:

- Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities (IIRC) led by Dist Prof Marcia Langton, University of Melbourne
- Establishing the Language Data Commons of Australia (LDA) led by Prof Michael Haugh, University of Queensland
- Developing Integrated Research Infrastructure for Social Sciences (IRISS) led by A/Prof Steven McEachern, Australian National University
- Creating the Trove Researcher Platform, which comprised Trove Enhancements (led by ANU) and the ARDC Community Data Lab (led by the ARDC)

In 2023, the ARDC received its largest-ever investment in HASS research infrastructure and Indigenous research capability. This \$25 million grant, part of the Australian Government's 2023 National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) Research Infrastructure Investment Plan Funding Round, supplemented by co-investment from national partners, will further establish long-term, national digital research infrastructure to support HASS and Indigenous research data communities in Australia.

Our commitment extends to supporting existing activities such as IIRC, LDA, the Community Data Lab, and Social Sciences while also considering the expansion of the RDC to include new activities for Creative Arts and Media(ted) Data. It has become evident that sustained investment is crucial to scale up these activities and provide coordinated digital research infrastructure meeting the needs of humanities, arts, social sciences, and Indigenous researchers.

Phase 2 aims to consolidate previous efforts, capitalise on synergies between existing and new projects, broaden partnerships and disciplinary coverage, and deepen engagement with the GLAM sector and Indigenous data governance.

In developing new activities, we have considered researcher needs gathered from consultations in 2021 and identified areas with active, coherent communities where research infrastructure can flourish. We have also looked at existing infrastructure that could be bolstered to transition into enduring national assets.

THE LANGUAGE DATA COMMONS OF AUSTRALIA

INVESTMENT OPPORTUNITY

The Language Data Commons of Australia (LDAcA) tackles the challenges researchers face in accessing and utilising language data for research. It addresses issues such as the disorganisation and potential loss of language data, difficulty in finding and accessing data, lack of standardised tools and methods, and underutilisation of existing collections with emphasis to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles while preserving language collections for future generations. Many valuable collections across Australia remain untapped resources due to inadequate organisation and accessibility. LDAcA seeks to rectify this by providing researchers with the necessary training, tools, and technical infrastructure to navigate and analyse language collections effectively.

LDAcA aims to support researchers to deliver innovative research outcomes, and opens up the social and economic possibilities of Australia's language data for translational research in the national interest by:

- balancing research needs while respecting community rights for language and cultural collections;
- highlighting contributions that language research and HASS disciplines can make to STEM research and non-academic applications; and
- positioning Australia internationally as a leading contributor of language collections and digital infrastructure.

LDAcA represents a transformative effort to make language data more accessible, usable, and impactful for research. By championing FAIR principles, preserving valuable collections, and fostering collaboration, LDAcA not only will advance the linguistic studies but also positions Australia as a leading contributor to language research and digital infrastructure on the global stage.

The proposed plan for the Language Data Commons of Australia is being developed through a process of co-design in collaboration with Australia's Academic and Research Network (AARNet), Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies (AIATSIS), Australian National University (ANU), Batchelor Institute of Indigenous Tertiary Education (BI), First Languages Australia (FLA), Queensland University of Technology's Digital Observatory (QUT-DO), The University of Melbourne (UoM), The University of Sydney (USyd), University of Western Australia (UWA) .

OUR CO-DESIGN PROCESS

The ARDC is developing this infrastructure in accordance with the HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10516606>). This process is designed to create the greatest impact for research and researchers by co-designing the infrastructure with the people who will benefit from it. Development will follow the stages of Problem Identification, Project Shaping, Project Planning, and Endorsement.

Problem Identification has taken place through extensive consultations and information gathering sessions, as described above. By tracking emerging gaps, opportunities, and sectoral trends, the ARDC has identified potential avenues for delivering benefits to the HASS and Indigenous research community. This strategic delineation of opportunities reflects the ARDC's commitment to addressing pertinent challenges and fostering innovation within the HASS and Indigenous research landscape.

The Project Shaping phase was implemented through the two open co-design workshops described below. Workshops were advertised through ARDC newsletters, social media channels and other networks. We sought to involve experts in research practice, disciplinary needs and infrastructure provision to better understand the current challenges faced by stakeholders and the outcomes that they hope to see, and to shape potential solutions that could be provided by the new infrastructure.

Project Planning and Endorsement phases will follow - further information is provided in the “Next Steps” section below.

WORKSHOP 1

The first co-design workshop was held virtually on 22 February 2024. It was attended by 35 participants from 21 organisations. Organisations represented included 15 Australian universities, as well as GLAM and research infrastructure organisations.

The aim of this first workshop was to refine our understanding of the challenge to be addressed and find out what outcomes participants want to achieve.

Professor Michael Haugh and Robert McLellan (LDaCA, the University of Queensland) presented on the challenge, which they summarised with the following problem statement:

“Australia is a massively multilingual country, in one of the world’s most linguistically diverse regions. Significant collections of this intangible cultural heritage have been

amassed. However, many collections remain under-utilised or at risk of being lost forever, and users often lack the tools and skills to exploit their research potential. We are faced with the challenge that language data is rarely organised or described in reusable ways, if it's described at all; it's difficult to know what language data exists and where to find it; processes for granting permissions and getting access to data are either absent or aren't easy to understand or apply; ad hoc tools, analysis and annotation methods are used, hampering reproducibility; and guides and training for collecting, handling and using data are scattered and hard to find."

Participants completed a series of discussion activities in breakout groups, and recorded their input using the Miro online whiteboard tool. Some key themes from the responses are highlighted below - full responses can be found in Appendix 1.

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

- What is the nature of the challenge we are trying to address? Is this stated clearly in the problem statement?
 - Difficulties with discovery and access of language data
 - Need for archiving and preservation of language data
 - Language data is nuanced and contextual - how do we maintain this while standardising and sharing?
 - Managing identifiability (particularly of data forms such as audio and video recordings)
 - Importance of delivering benefit back to the language-using community
 - Managing time needed to work effectively with communities
 - Important to consider needs of non-research users of the infrastructure
 - Need for clarity on which forms of data are included
 - Need for good governance of infrastructure and data
- Who does this challenge affect? (Who needs a solution?)
 - Researchers and research support staff
 - Language users
 - Data custodians

- What limitations are created by this challenge?
 - Difficulty managing the balance between allowing access and protecting data
 - Risks to the sustainability of data collections and tools
 - Duplication of effort
- What could we achieve by addressing it?
 - Better data discovery
 - Better research
 - Protect and preserve languages
 - Increased data skills for researchers
 - Shared tools for collective benefit
 - New opportunities for machine learning
- Who could benefit?
 - Researchers
 - Language users
 - Schools and students
 - GLAM sector

Activity 2: Outcomes and opportunities

- What outcomes would be beneficial?
 - Strengthen relationships between researchers and communities
 - Build community trust in research and researchers
 - Support appropriate community control of data
 - Support good access management for data
 - Agreed processes, protocols and workflows
 - Improve data discovery and search
 - Better data description and metadata
 - Enhanced data
 - Support sustainability and preservation

- Appropriate and accessible interfaces for a range of users
- Empower potential users with access to data
- Provide analytical tools
- Provide resources and guidance
- What existing infrastructure/activities could we build on?
 - Participants gave an extensive list of existing platforms, organisations and initiatives that could be leveraged - see Appendix 1

Activity 3: Roles and partners

- What other kinds of partners need to be involved?
 - Potential holders of language data (GLAM organisations, broadcasters, researchers)
 - Technical infrastructure providers
- What other expertise/resources would benefit the project?
 - Expertise in data governance
 - Expertise in metadata
 - Expertise in training and research support
 - Ethical and legal expertise
 - User experience expertise
- Whose perspectives and input would make this project better?
 - Students
 - Educators

WORKSHOP 2

The second co-design workshop was held virtually on 7 March 2024. It was attended by 35 participants from 17 organisations. Organisations represented included 9 Australian universities, an international university, as well as GLAM and research infrastructure organisations.

The aim of this workshop was to explore how the desired outcomes identified by participants in Workshop 1 could be achieved within the new infrastructure investment, and understand requirements and practical considerations for the potential solutions.

Staff from the ARDC reported back on the key findings from Workshop 1. Based on the responses to the Workshop 1 question “What outcomes would be beneficial”, we drew out three high-level outcome themes:

- “Support meaningful research relationships and data access management for communities”, based on responses about strengthening relationships between researchers and communities; building community trust in research and researchers; supporting appropriate community control of data; supporting good access management for data; and the need for agreed processes, protocols and workflows (relating to community engagement, data capture and data access).
- “Improve the description, discovery and reuse of language data”, based on responses about improving data discovery and search, better description and metadata, enhancing data, and supporting sustainability and preservation.
- “Increase user capability and confidence with LDaCA infrastructure”, based on responses about a need for resources and guidance; appropriate and accessible interfaces for a range of users; empowering potential users; providing analytical tools; and the need for agreed processes, protocols and workflows (relating to data management and analysis).

We addressed each of these three outcome themes in turn. For each theme, Professor Michael Haugh and Robert McLellan (LDaCA, the University of Queensland) outlined a range of approaches and solutions that could be taken to achieve that outcome. In breakout groups, the workshop participants discussed those approaches, noting any requirements they would have for these approaches to be successful, and any practical considerations to be taken into account. Participants recorded their input using the Miro online whiteboard tool. Common themes from the responses are recorded below, and full responses are attached in Appendix 2.

Support meaningful research relationships and data access management for communities

- Approach: Policy frameworks and implementation strategies
 - Policy frameworks should reflect community needs - including flexibility to change in community relationships
 - Work to align with existing frameworks within organisations and learn from other disciplines
- Approach: Language data licences
 - Licensing challenges for historical data
 - Clarify the process of arranging licences

- Is it possible to create templates or wizards to assist with the creation of licences, given the complexity of the necessary arrangements?
- Approach: Tools and processes for authorised access to repositories and workspaces
 - Ensure accessibility outside of AAF (LDAcA currently achieves this using CILogin)
 - Registration of the planned use of the data when requesting access
 - User-friendly interfaces to repositories and workspaces that meet user needs and expectations
 - Good documentation, guides and examples

Improve the description, discovery and reuse of language data

- Approach: Discovery and annotation of language materials in GLAM and other existing institutions
 - Importance of rigorous and consistent metadata
 - Ability to search by theme across organisations/institutions
 - Use of AI, automation and OCR to speed process (see Nyingarn)
 - Use of crowdsourcing to improve description (but note quality concerns)
- Approach: Data portals
 - User-friendly interfaces based on user needs
 - Importance of good vocabularies and metadata schemas
 - Ability for users to assign private, bespoke tags to search results
 - Be clear about where data is stored - show the range of different sources
 - Build portals on standard API framework - user interfaces should be loosely coupled with the data
- Approach: Community-controlled workspaces for researchers and communities
 - Build relationships between researchers and communities, technical and non-technical groups
 - Inclusivity - instructions, guidance etc. in multiple languages and formats (audio, video)

Increase user capability and confidence with LDAcA infrastructure

- Approach: Building relationships with and capability in data custodians

- “Custodian” can be a complex and shifting concept in some communities - how to identify and define their role?
- Active role in research for data custodians - named investigators, research bursaries
- Approach: Language and text analytics notebooks and tools
 - Alternatives to notebooks - can present a barrier to entry for some users, and not all projects fit the notebook paradigm
 - Managing version control for notebooks as they are updated
 - Sharing existing/externally developed tools - don’t try and develop all of the tools within LDaCA
- Approach: Training for data users in use of LDaCA infrastructure and tools
 - Tools and workflows should be intuitive enough to require minimal training (but note that what is intuitive to one person may not be intuitive to another)
 - Video tutorials (but note the high cost of updating these when tools change)
 - Integrate LDaCA training into student coursework
 - Concrete use cases and examples that are relevant and interesting to the specific audience
 - Discussion forums and communities for peer support

NEXT STEPS

The ARDC has worked with the potential project team to develop a draft project plan, released for public feedback alongside the publication of this report. Feedback submissions will close at the end of day, Friday 22 March. To submit feedback on project plans please use the form on the ARDC website. All feedback will be collated and responded to in a published report, alongside an updated project plan taking into account this feedback wherever possible. Work on this project is planned to commence in July 2024.

The development of the resulting infrastructure will involve ongoing public testing and consultation - please make sure you are signed up to the HASS and I newsletter so that you receive notifications about upcoming opportunities to be involved.

If you have any other comments or questions about this process please contact us at hassi.codesign@ardc.edu.au with the subject line “LDaCA”.

APPENDIX 1: WORKSHOP 1 RESPONSES

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What is the nature of the challenge we are trying to address? Is this stated clearly in the problem statement?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Would be good to mention something about best practice in regards to data governance ● Data archives and research project datasets have different requirements and different governance - take care not to conflate the two ● The statement feels comprehensive to me. The key challenges will be in the detail -- what kinds of data are included and excluded (only text? how does audio get included and indexed for content?). This does feel like a data-centric definition; users other than researchers aren't clearly centered here. ● The nature of the audience in this workshop (almost all academics) reflects one of the public engagement challenges for LDaCA ● lack of tools and skills' is very oriented to researchers. How can the unskilled and untooled benefit from these collections? ● Is 'research potential' the only/main use of the data? Members of the public/speakers of the languages might not be aiming to 'research' the collections. (+2) ● "Is 'research potential' the only/main use of the data? Members of the public/speakers of the languages might not be aiming to 'research' the collections. " - Yes, a major benefit is the virtue of making research data available so that the general public can access it, in particular, people recorded and their descendants ● End-user access/interface design is a very important design issue which will differ considerably across populations -- e.g. the needs of secondary school language students are very different from those of researchers and community members will of course have very different needs again. (+1) ● Definition required of who the users are. If the answer is everyone then this needs segmentation (specialist scholars, general scholars, HRD, schools students, general public, host communities...

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● This needs another consideration - People - this is about people, which requires MORE time and that's what we don't have enough of ● Another problem to look into is the time as a challenge which is not reflected in here ● The challenge doesn't give any sense of the outcomes or benefits for the community. It seems to presume the benefits (for linguists) but what will be the broader benefits? ● Growing awareness of need to give back to community where data is collected ● are community members' contributions always volunteering/free labour? ● We have to have the data first. Then worry about how we access it later. ● Supporting language revitalisation through building technologies and systems to make language data appropriately discoverable and accessible. ● Lack of accessibility and discoverability of relevant data (+1) ● finding, collecting, accessing, and sharing data ● Probably ensuring data sovereignty as a concept should be mentioned somewhere here -- permissions are but the reason permissions matter is data privacy and data sovereignty issues, which commercial AI systems do not respect ● ethics of deidentified data vs ownership of contributions ● "ethics of deidentified data vs ownership of contributions" - + with sign languages, you can't deidentify the data - face and body are important in understanding meaning ● language is a type of cultural data. to understand it, it needs to be contextualised (+1) ● Is ad-hoc really bad? That might also be positive in the sense of situated/specific to context (+1) ● Hard to make research data sharable and maintain richness and nuance ● Preservation and capturing existing data in agreed format ● One aspect that might be missing there is that digitisation of archival materials is a huge technical challenge and an expensive one. But if archival materials cannot be digitised they cannot be accessed through initiatives such as this.

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Need a standard for how to carry digitised collections forward as technology changes & old formats become unusable ● Capture first on stable IT/ formats, Assess later, Have a defined standard to capture going forward. ● The use of 'significant' collection may imply that less significant ones will not be included and also necessitates a way of defining 'significance' (+2) ● "The use of 'significant' collection may imply that less significant ones will not be included and also necessitates a way of defining 'significance'" - The relevant (language) community should be involved in deciding what is significant ● Prioritisation of effort will be very important to address transparently, as there will be competition for the resources of this initiative and who decides what data efforts get supported and how will matter to end-users. ● Are you only interested in existing and archival data? What about new and emerging forms of online language data ● The statement doesn't give any sense that it is building on work that has happened so far. It could be the same as 2 years ago. ● Standardised and repeatable processes also aid efficiency, which is a critical stumbling block for archives with little funding and ability to access technical support for their work. Efficiency needs to be explicitly mentioned in the challenge statement (or the barrier that inefficiency creates). At the moment it;s just implicit. ● Rapid changes: * technology *legal * cultural *research processes and techniques ● People centred, not knowledge centred ● Lack of a common framework for different data collections ● It's pretty clear, it's just broad. I realise that's out of necessity, but perhaps some guiding principles would balance out that extreme openness? ● Definition needed of who is a researcher. specialist, general scholar, student. ● Data that is within two categories - e.g. Indigenous sign language, Croatian-speaking oral history ● Change in the volume of what can be collected

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Challenge statement probably needs some reference to the ethical issues around "access to data"; ● Audit all sites language data sits create a space to capture Creation of AI to recognise languages or ID formats (+2) ● advantages of contemporary digital data principles and process - eg. LOD ● Acknowledgement of Indigenous Knowledge systems vs making their Languages and subsequent data to "f\text" into wWestern knowledge systems ● A key challenge is also the hegemony of English – but perhaps that's a bit political for a big state-funded project...
<p>Who does this challenge affect? (Who needs a solution?)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data custodians, researchers, language communities ● Insitutions responsible for preservation and access of digital material ● researchers, language users, government and policy makers ● Cultural owners (+1) ● Indigenous people - any language group without access to their own language ● First Nations communities ● Improvement in this space would be super helpful for research support staff - having clear standards and best practices to follow rather than having to figure everything out from scratch (+1) ● Research software engineers – who are trying to work out what researchers need (+1) ● researchers need skills - digital and otherwise - to be able to access/create collections ● AI/ML/LLM researchers ● it will make it easier for the non-linguists to collaborate in this space (+2) ● Language learners at all levels including tertiary, where language studies are in severe decline. Connecting this effort with language learning -- since language learners will be among the maintainers of this data in future -- feels really important. ● Engagement with different user segments requires different UX ● The public, school students - who have an obligation to understand our diverse community (+1) ● UX needs to be appropriate for researcher/user segment

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What limitations are created by this challenge?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● User interface on data portal is for an archivist rather than a researcher ● Duplication of effort and waste of resources ● Is reproducibility really a core problem, or just a symptom? Feels like transparency, reusability, avoiding unnecessary duplication might be better goals (+1) ● "Is reproducibility really a core problem, or just a symptom?" - I agree. Reproducibility is a real problem – but the bigger issue with 'ad hoc'-ness is that it is difficult to build a scholarly community when there isn't an agreed core of methods and technologies that everyone's used to. ● Reluctance to allow access to sensitive data ● How we navigate the expectation about making data accessible, and the ethical/moral/legal obligations that often place restrictions on data sharing. ● In some cases legislation will inhibit access i.e. IP legislation ● LDaCA has an important role here, because it makes data accessible BUT with necessary restrictions ● Pulled in two directions - 1. Accessibility and Open Science 2. CARE and respecting community ● what happens to the research infrastructure after funding runs out? (+2) ● funding sustainability ● how are you planning to capture the data in a sustainable way? ● Is there even a problem with ad-hocness? I feel there are a core set of tools and methods for working with language data (especially AntConc, Python's NLTK and R's tidytext). The problem is probably more with audiovisual materials, which are admittedly much harder to use computationally. ● current language data focus on text data. it is essential to address other modes - such as audio, video, and social media (+2) ● Researchers don't know what best practice is for managing their data ● Changes to publications requirements - need to make data accessible with publication ● Community language workers volunteering their time (not being paid to do language research (+2) ● limitations of available data platforms/ systems/practices

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Limited access data: both digital and physical (+1) ● Never enough time ● Not just a lack of digital skills, but also governance, ethics (+1) ● Not knowing where to find data (+1) ● Take care that this doesn't just become an engineering problem - it's as much a social and policy problem as a technical one (+1) ● technical skills to implement and deploy the tools
<p>What could we achieve by addressing it?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Better return on research investment ● better research ● better enabling of research ● This is part of the broader aim to recognise/cherish linguistic and cultural diversity in the region. Only if the majority-language majority recognise the value of minority languages will they commit the necessary resources to revitalisation. ● The ultimate goal should be language revitalisation and sustainability ● Keeping languages alive (+1) ● better protection of data/knowledge for communities ● can be used to train LLMs (+1) ● ML/AI training datasets ● Greater discoverability and interoperability of data, subject to access conditions (+3) ● discovery and exploration of different datasets ● tools, principles, services developed thru LDaCA should benefit other commons/domains (+1) ● modular and interoperable tools and methods provide scaffolding for all to climb higher ● upskilling of HASS researchers ● Increased data literacy and language technology literacy among humanities researchers (+1) ● increased awareness & skills of researchers in data governance and text analytics ● improved skills for researchers ● Shared language for *discussing* language datasets and analysis ● reduce duplication of efforts and investments across research institutions

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● More perspectives on and insight from existing data rather than it fading into obscurity ● Improved trust between data owners and researchers (+2) ● Greater collaboration across research domains ● better linkages across collections (esp for small languages) where samples may exist in single records across multiple separate collections/institutions ● Increasing linked/linkable data ● An enriched sense of cultural heritage and history, at a time when focus on the future may detract from attention to and investment in remembering the past ● "An enriched sense of cultural heritage and history, at a time when focus on the future may detract from attention to and investment in remembering the past" - And enriched sense of cultural heritage and history is a benefit to all and should be part of the broader aims but we need to be careful about speaking about this in terms of 'remembering the past'. Indigenous cultures are evolve just like all others and are both ancient and modern. ● Allowing data custodians and owners to see that their work providing the data is worthwhile, that it's being used and used well. (+1)
<p>Who could be benefited by addressing this challenge?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NLA/GLAM sector, by assisting in identifying relevant collections and sharing advice re managing permission etc. ● Industry users, including but not limited to GLAM sector (+1) ● Academic community: researchers, students etc in HASS (+1) ● Community languages teachers and students at all levels ● Students in many discipline could benefit from datasets to use in class ● Schools who are increasingly looking to integrate FN languages and culture into their curriculums ● The users of the languages MUST benefit (+ 2) ● and communities whose languages are represented - language revitalisation, recording culture ● First Nations communities ● Non-linguistics researchers, and research support staff ● anthropologists, social psychologists, IT working with language models ● Researchers need upskilling in long-term management of digital data

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● linguists, historians, philosophers - anyone with questions that you can answer with analysis of language collections ● Researchers are not aware of best practice for managing digital language data (+1) ● "Researchers are not aware of best practice for managing digital language data" - so, LDACA can be involved in training researchers in data management and curation ● "Researchers are not aware of best practice for managing digital language data" - Best practice is a backward-looking criterion. Linguists have often led the way in data standards (e.g. OLAC, language ISO codes) – what is more important than 'best practice' is some agreed principles for improvement of linguistic data collection/management/use. ● lexicographers - finding out how language develops, examples ● Sign language data set users ● support for disabled people ● non-traditional users of language e.g. speech pathologist ● Community users ('ordinary' people) ● Collecting institutions would benefit from having well described data that facilitates more autonomous appropriate access to collections by users

Activity 2: Outcomes and opportunities

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What outcomes would be beneficial?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Preserving existing data, but with ways to add further metadata, linkages to the original. Ways for enhancements to be fed back in without compromising the original ● Data can be worked with, but also preserved sufficiently for future use ● Building trust between Language users and Indigenous communities trusting researchers/ collecting institutions so they feel safe working collaboratively to achieve language sustainability ● A language archive guaranteed for perpetuity (+2) ● creation of reference corpora and making them accessible ● ways of gaining access to data that aren't dependent on one person checking their emails (+1) ● F.A.I.R. language data ● Appropriate access to Indigenous language records that are currently held hostage by holding institutions ● Agreed standards and processes for capturing and handling the data, and access by those who aren't owners. (+1) ● tools for small agencies to organise their language collections (language centres, oral history societies etc) (+2) ● recognition of non-traditional outcomes such as data citations to encourage data sharing. (+3) ● Indigenous leadership in language research for each FN ● Describe LDaCA outputs in plain language ● Gaining an understanding of Australia's history from diverse perspectives - history typically told from an Anglo perspective, but there is a wealth of information available in e.g. oral histories collected across Australia's (+2) ● Opening up captured languages and letting language owners identify / reclassify them ● Corrections by public ● include annotation of images & videos in scope ● Duolingo-style language games for minority languages in our region ● Data robust enough for re-interpretation/enquiry in future ● connect ● Concept of 'my collection'

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Community - working groups, mailing lists, forums - any avenues for groups to discuss various elements and keep working on/with them after LDACA is gone ● Australia becoming an international leader in managing language data (+3) ● Analysing data we need today, but having the data available that we can interrogate and may need in the future, through a future lens ● All languages recorded require digitisation so language students can privilege Aboriginal languages over Polish or turkish or French etc ● A widespread understanding that data must be validated to be useful. Poor quality data can be worse than no data at all, especially if users assume "data = truth" (+2) ● A policy tool/checklist for embedding CARE into ethics approvals/institutional repositories etc. ● a large national language data research group/lab working on shared problems, providing career paths for researchers and data specialists ● a "fair-use" way of sharing copyrighted data for analysis by others ● "text" doesn't necessarily mean just written text (note this term is used differently across research communities) (+1) ● "a "fair-use" way of sharing copyrighted data for analysis by others" - The federal government has been conducting a review in copyright. The research community is present and is pushing for some kind of 'fair use' in Australia – unfortunately the publishers have good lobbyists! ● More resources like the PARADISEC map that enable non-experts to understand the content of collections (+1) ● Different entry points and training for different user groups ● Develop generous interfaces to support non specialist. Enquiry as well as specialist research. ● Comprehensive process of defining researcher segments mapped to UX affordances. (+1) ● Making data practices and stewardship and use something that everyone feels comfortable with, not just software engineers and linguists and social scientists. There seems to be a big gap between the data-engaged and the data-disengaged at the present time (+2)

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Greater confidence from the broader community that they can make good use of what's out there ● Data available for communities to re-empower them and also have their voice(s) heard. Increase learning of indigenous languages. ● Standoff annotation of objects to support bespoke research on "my collection" ● Workflows and use cases ● When its people-centred, theres ongoing relationships between Country-Language-People-Researcher-Institution ● Treatment of searches as virtual collections for bespoke research ● The ability for language students (Indigenous and community languages) to discover historical and linguistic material that will inspire their learning and continued engagement with their language(s) ● Standardised ways of marking up / translating language data ● Standardisation ● Shared tools across disciplines eg ATAP ● Ongoing and long term relationships supported post any research and language work. -Not the oldwer model of "i did my phd on this language in the bush, I get my green light but i leave the communit and the language back in the bush and never see them again" ie, long term relationships between researcher, institution and the people and language on the ground ● metadata and annotation on images ● "metadata and annotation on images" - Collaborative annotation tools in general! ● Linked data between archival and GLAM repositories so that history/creativity/memory can be brought together in any search ● Increased visibility of existing datasets for multiple uses (if that's what the community wants) (+1) ● Improved discoverability (based on strong metadata practices but also digitisation of audio and video materials and indexing of these) will be the foundation stone for access ● Improved data collecting standards that stem the tide of orphan/unlocatable/undescribed data (+1) ● Guidelines for new collections

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Frictionless/interoperable searching ability across institutions/collections (+1) ● Easy to navigate catalogue of available resources and associated metadata as well as (if it's speech data) information re: recording conditions etc. ● Community controlled keeping places for language data ● "Community controlled keeping places for language data" - yes, ideally backed up by an agency like AIATSIS to ensure the materials are safe ● Closing the loop between language data custodians and language data 'users' -> transparency and trust (+2) ● Clear protocols for existing data sets that cannot be retrospectively changed AND protocols to "do it right" with future datasets. Do not have to be the same ● Clear and simple workflows (+1) ● Clear and accessible best practices both for storing/describing data and for working with it (+1) ● "Clear and accessible best practices both for storing/describing data and for working with it " - e.g. clear labelling of library/institutional holdings with ISO codes ● Building digital guidelines as well to people back in the center and build and instil trust (+1) ● better use of resources by reducing researchers re-inventing the wheel (eg open sharing of tools rather than ad hoc individual solutions) ● Balancing language communities having control over their own data with the fact that they could get a lot of requests for access to data (i.e. workload concerns) ● analytic tools for text and other modes of data ● An open/interactive textbook in language data management ● "An open/interactive textbook in language data management" - https://mitpress.mit.edu/9780262362177/the-open-handbook-of-linguistic-data-management/ ● AI language functionality to aid language structures for all Indigenous languages

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ability to use crowdsourcing to enhance existing collections (some carefully managed, some less closely managed) ● A complete toolchain for RO-Crate
<p>What existing infrastructure/ activities could we build on?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The question is "build on", but also need to ask about who to *work with* (+1) ● network graph as a UX metaphor, an augment to metadata centric UX ● It sounds a bit cold but perhaps relationships need to be considered as critical infrastructure to the success of this project. Good technical systems are great, but building strong relationships between language users, researchers and collecting institutions will underpin the sustainability of the project. ● Extend scope to include collections significant to Australians and Australian researchers not limited to Australian texts. ● "Extend scope to include collections significant to Australians and Australian researchers not limited to Australian texts. " - LDACA has a Pacific focus too, would that be included in this? ● Data existing that we don't know about (+2) ● Wikipedia has 300 language editions and Wikidata is a multilingual database that could be incorporated ● "Wikipedia has 300 language editions and Wikidata is a multilingual database that could be incorporated" - Wasn't there some controversy over the Scotts Wikipedia turning out to have been mostly written by one kid using a Scotts dictionary, rather than fluent speakers? ● "Wikipedia has 300 language editions ... - Wasn't there some controversy over the Scotts Wikipedia..." - Yes, there are several controversies over Wikipedia's minority languages. There are several Filipino languages whose Wikipedias are the result of machine translation. ● Various open-source communication and discussion platforms and tools - work in the open and allow others to read and join in ● Useful to have smooth interfaces to widely-used tools for speech analysis such as Praat or LaBB-CAT. ● Universities that have research data infrastructure already, dataset publication infrastructure etc - how to standardise it, how they can incorporate requirements/recommendations/best practice ● TK Labels & Notices

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The Nectar research cloud – especially its JupyterLab instance ● Sound archives, e.g. Scotland's sounds could be a model. So it's not all textual/visual/verbal - cultural history can also be acoustic (+1) ● Sensitive data access protocols and platforms ● Open Language Archives Community (OLAC), needs to revamped ● "Open Language Archives Community (OLAC), needs to revamped" - In general? Or thinking specifically about metadata? For the second, LDaCA has built on the OLAC vocabulary. ● "Open Language Archives Community (OLAC), needs to revamped" - "In general? Or thinking specifically about metadata?..." In general, OLAC is a great service but is on its last legs ● open access licensing norms (+1) ● "open access licensing norms" - Can only apply in a subset of cases ● Mukurtu https://mukurtu.org/ ● International digital identifier services. Eg: datacite DOIs for data sets, storage infrastructure, researchers and administrative staff... ● IIF annotations can be searched and filtered ● https://localcontexts.org/labels/traditional-knowledge-labels/ ● Glottolog, and Austlang need to be integrated into OLAC ● free' commercial CDNs (netlify, github pages etc) – e.g. to publish research or teaching materials ● For metadata: DublinCore metadata standards ● Existing techniques for language data analysis ● "Existing powerful tools for text analysis: NLTK, R ecosystem, Antconc." - And https://orangedatamining.com/download/ ● Existing reference management tools – all LDaCA collections should be machine-citable using the opengraph standard developed by Google Scholar (compatible with Zotero, Mendeley, Endnote etc) – https://scholar.google.com/intl/en/scholar/inclusion.html#indexing (+1) ● Existing powerful tools for text analysis: NLTK, R ecosystem, Antconc. ● Endangered Languages Archive ● ELPIS for audio transcription (with substantial investment in improvements) ● Elan (for annotation) - but it also could be better / smoother ● Digitised oral histories in GLAM collections, eg NLA and SLNSW

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Datacite 4.5 schema ● Could be extended with an RStudio instance in the cloud, to support ATAP's preferred language ● Central repository of data, like the Svalbard Global Seed Vault ● becoming part of undergraduate skills and training programs ● become a part of the broader GLAM referral practice - ensure that GLAM professionals know about the LDaCA program and can refer researchers and patrons to language data (ppl often start at GLAM first when setting out to find language information) (+1) ● And CIDOC-CRM, and schema.org

Activity 3: Roles and partners

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What other kinds of partners need to be involved?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● GLAM - need to identify language content in their collections and make that information available in online catalogues with APIs (+2) ● University archives (e.g. Dardalis Archive at La Trobe for Greek community archival material) ● Local museums and historical societies (+1) ● University libraries - universities have data management plans, but libraries re not always able to offer the services needed for language collections ● GLAM Peak ● HCI researchers, Computer scientists, data scientists - for both technical perspectives and as users ● Other research infrastructure facilities and providers (+1) ● Open source communities - where using open source tools etc ● Wikimedia - 300 different language wikipedias (+1) ● Contemporary ethnographers and anthropologists who collect useful linguistic samples incidentally ● Maybe some public broadcasting bodies (ABS/SBS for example) who are sitting on large repositories of the relevant data but with this being largely difficult to access) ● "Maybe some public broadcasting bodies (ABS/SBS for example) ... " - SBS radio is an enticing possibility

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Call out to all researchers working within communities, to gather all language data in all subject areas, that that has not been deposited anywhere ● Kids who want to learn language ● MOre community voices ● Oral history societies (+2) ● Digital Observatory LDACA ● speech therapists and pathologists ● I've heard some interesting things out of the Mozilla Common Voice community - very different project but might be worth a chat ● www.asdo.org.au ● Other ARDC funded projects inc new streams ● Social media companies ● Music-related organisations? Song being a point of cross-over with language (+2) ● "Music-related organisations? Song being a point of cross-over with language" - For example collaborating on songwriting workshops in languages other than English with QMusic perhaps? ● Contact The Northern Institute at Charles Darwin University as a potential partner.
<p>What other expertise/ resources would benefit the project?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ABC? SBS? for the stories that exist in collections being identified (+2) ● Cultural studies, historian researchers articulate UX that might work for them. (+1) ● Digitisation experts (+1) ● ELPIS , speech to text methods for annotating untranscribed media (+1) ● Get tertiary language students and academics involved (as researchers but also, resources, e.g. via internships)! Language studies departments are dwindling fast and this involvement could demonstrate the ongoing relevance of community language transmission. (+1) ● Human-Computer Interaction / UX experts (+4) ● We need an online media annotation tool to allow crowdsourced textual versions of media ● Metadata experts

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "Metadata experts" - Local Contexts for attribution, provenance & protocol metadata ● Parts of institutions responsible for training - particularly at HDR level? ● Skilling researchers in data transformation to onboard collections might be not the most effective approach. ● university eResearch/research infrastructure groups, research support staff, libraries, research data librarians - those support people all over the country who have been helping with the ad-hoc projects you describe and were learning lessons and probably hoping for better the whole time (+1) ● Upskilling community to allow greater growth in the communities where the data originates ● ethics and legal expertise ● "ethics and legal expertise"- Terri Janke & Co. might be a good one. ● data governance expertise (+1) ● "data governance expertise" - Maiam nayri Wingari & GIDA
<p>Whose perspectives and input would make this project better?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Members of the general public. Also community librarians, who are sometimes the main interface with community and culture for townships that are lucky enough to have a library. (+3) ● Community voices need to be more highly privileged ● performers. -dance, musicians, who work in the cultural sector ● Digital preservation ● language societies ● Consulting services to automate onboarding of collections ● academies of humanities and social sciences ● government and policy makers ● Great project conducted in the UK - 'Unlocking Our Sound Heritage'; might be worth talking to someone involved in that: https://blogs.bl.uk/sound-and-vision/2021/02/250000-sounds-preserved-by-unlocking-our-sound-heritage.html ● The open data and open government communities will have relevant lessons learned (+2) ● Primary, secondary and tertiary level educators, who can use these resources in the classroom (+3) ● "Primary, secondary and tertiary level educators, who can use these resources in the classroom" - There is a challenge here, because

QUESTION	RESPONSES
	<p>Australasian/Pacific languages are only rarely on the curriculum. It would be good to work through bodies such as the Secondary Principal's Council or AFMLTA who can actually alter the curriculum.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Of course, there are the community language schools ● Students who will potentially go on to do research ● "Students who will potentially go on to do research" - Creating training pathways into digital/data-driven research would be awesome

APPENDIX 2: WORKSHOP 2 RESPONSES

Outcome 1: Support meaningful research relationships and data access management for communities

APPROACH	RESPONSES
<p>Policy frameworks and implementation strategies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How does an existing archive like PARADISEC relate? ● "How does an existing archive like PARADISEC relate?" - PARADISEC is a partner in LDACA ● research data sharing policy ● Policies (enforceable) about who can/should hold/publish language datasets ● "Policies (enforceable) about who can/should hold/publish language datasets" - I've now been at 2 universities whose data policies include "We, the university, own the data collected by our researchers", which goes against the spirit of community control over their own data. But on the positive side, they have the resources and infrastructure to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1. store and publish datasets ○ 2. enforce licence terms (at least in theory) ● Might need to involve granting bodies to set/enforce terms for where data can be stored/published " ● would be great to have clear gov'n't policy plan/help to capture and preserve work carried out at language centres. ● "would be great to have clear gov'n't policy plan/help to capture and preserve work carried out at language centres." - Isn't this what AIATSIS should be doing? (+1) ● "would be great to have clear gov'n't policy plan/help to capture and preserve work carried out at language centres." - "Isn't this what AIATSIS should be doing? (+1)" - Yes, but are they...? ● From my work in some communities, "access control" is NOT about access really but about the known social map of who knows what (including language usage of all kinds) and who has the right to various aspects of sharing. ie protocol/access is dynamic over time and negotiated. ● Also community control should not so often look like an add-on afterthought, but the needs and consequences of access WITHIN a

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<p>community should be considered. For example, when some language knowledge is shared, the whole social "map" has changed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Draw from ICIP, IDS, CARE maturity model ● Across all three columns: sharing your learnings and offering advice, tools, templates for other repositories, data custodians, infrastructure providers etc. Bonus points for not just offering documentation, but creating communities of practice! ● What can we promise communities about sustainability? ● Need to develop data governance frameworks which can be informed by existing data governance frameworks in other orgs ● policy to protect sharing data amongst researchers (+1) ● Thinking of implementation: to get communities on board, we need to understand their needs, and show them that LDaCA is of relevance/useful to them - how do we do that? What kinds of things would help communities see the value of LDaCA? ● "Thinking of implementation: to get communities on board, we need to understand their needs, and show them that LDaCA is of relevance/useful to them - how do we do that? What kinds of things would help communities see the value of LDaCA?" -Developing exemplar projects is a good strategy. ● Consider cultural governance & decision making. relating to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● All policy framework design ● Implementation ● Operations / process / management / evaluation ● Researcher relationship development & engagement on Country, as process. ● Recognise the 'researcher' potential of community members ● Can we draw from experience in other domains such as medical data? ● policy alignment with other data custodians ● What do communities say about the best ways to build trust ● "What do communities say about the best ways to build trust" - what communities? ● From my work in some communities, "access control" is NOT about access really but about the known social map of who knows what (including language usage of all kinds) and who has the right to

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<p>various aspects of sharing. ie protocol/access is dynamic over time and negotiated. Also community control should not so often look like an add-on afterthought, but the needs and consequences of access WITHIN a community should be considered. For example, when some language knowledge is shared, the whole social "map" has changed</p>
<p>Language data licences</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Has anyone successfully implemented Traditional Knowledge licences? ● "Has anyone successfully implemented Traditional Knowledge licences?" - Licences are yet to be completed by Local Contexts ● relationship based licencing ● "relationship based licencing" - What does this mean? - You have to build relationships with communities / data custodians before being allowed to access data ● "relationship based licencing" - Ben Foley and Janet Wiles at UQ have done work in this space ● GDPR - e.g. data must be able to be taken down if requested. ● How do we classify historical data? Sometimes a blanket policy can be too restrictive or permissive ● "How do we classify historical data? Sometimes a blanket policy can be too restrictive or permissive" - LDaCA does not have blanket policies. Licences can be specific down to individual data items. ● "How do we classify historical data? Sometimes a blanket policy can be too restrictive or permissive" - Historical data pose interesting problems where they material is not protected by copyright (if that was ever relevant), has been made available but some people may still have moral rights relevant to the material. ● clear process for getting licences ● "clear process for getting licences" -Licences need to be written - they're not out there waiting to be got ● "clear process for getting licences" - potentially an invasion of privacy to attempt to keep people's relationships in a data store? ● clear process for issuing licences - requirements, what institution(s) could issue licences

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● " clear process for issuing licences - requirements, what institution(s) could issue licences" -Often individuals hold copyright and it is copyright holders who issue licences ● When in doubt about a licence, prefer making material available: consider that Indigenous people need to have access to material in their own languages and that GLAM can repeat past problems by hiding behind ICIP to prevent access (+1) ● Consider what an ideal licence would be for data just starting to be collected... will be different to the legacy data can of worms ● Cultural knowledge agreements ● between publisher / all clans connected to language or dialect. Exploring feasibility of copyright, trademark ● Cultural IP as royalty stream ● Templates, wizards - utilities for data custodians new to this space. Examples: Creative Commons https://chooser-beta.creativecommons.org/; https://choosealicense.com/ (+1) ● "Templates, wizards - utilities for data custodians new to this space. Examples: Creative Commons ..." - CC is relatively simple as it is about open access - where access needs to be controlled it is MUCH more complicated -- we are a long way from being able to have wizards etc ● "Templates, wizards - utilities for data custodians new to this space. Examples: Creative Commons ..." - " CC is relatively simple as it is about open access - where access needs to be controlled it is MUCH more complicated ..." - Fair enough - at least some examples would help to give people a starting point which they can pull pieces from and adapt to what's appropriate for their data ● Need help for Data stewards who are not necessarily well versed with data licences, particularly if they need a custom licence because none of the CC licences are suitable for their context. (+1) ● LDaCA has created documentation about licensing, and key considerations (available on the portal) - how to circulate these more widely, and get feedback from communities - people are not necessarily used to thinking about this, so there is some acculturation that needs to be done (+@)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
<p>Tools and processes for authorised access to repositories and workspaces</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Community consultation (across all stakeholder communities) ● Access for data mining, AI and ML makes this complex and needs to be allowed for ● TK Labels & Notices are an effective tool for nuanced access and use protocols ● Infrastructure must be accessible by people outside AAF (+4) ● "Infrastructure must be accessible by people outside AAF" - Already implemented. CILogin allows authentication with Orcid, Google. ● Clear identification of who has the right/responsibility to authorise access ● alarm or notification when unauthorised access occurs ● Like pre-registering experiments for publication, perhaps some way to pre-register what the language data will be used for, as part of the request to access/licence data (+3) ● "Like pre-registering experiments for publication, perhaps some way to pre-register what the language data will be used for, as part of the request to access/licence data" - We have this in place for Sydney Speaks (+1) ● "Like pre-registering experiments for publication, perhaps some way to pre-register what the language data will be used for, as part of the request to access/licence data" - this sort of thing really makes data custodians and participants feel the value of the work they've done ● linking Native Title bodies to data ● "linking Native Title bodies to data" - Authority and ID-SOV concerns there.. ● clear access protocols ● protection from being used as training data for LLMs (+1) ● familiar and user-friendly user interfaces to repositories and workspaces (+3) ● "familiar and user-friendly user interfaces to repositories and workspaces" -that meets community expectations of what they would expect to see, and to do that, we need to understand what it is they expect; this also applies to researchers, as different disciplines have different expectations

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "familiar and user-friendly user interfaces to repositories and workspaces" - including perhaps easy access for community members (speakers, performers, lang contributors) ● Are there other emerging/emerged standards, interfaces, infrastructures in other fields of the social sciences that LDACA can interface with/be available to/partner with etc? Don't forget the world outside linguistics! ● Good documentation is essential! Overviews, tutorials, guides, and references are all needed for technical integration to go smoothly (+3) ● Data attribution - should be clear how data will be attributed / how to cite (+1) ● Examples and/or reference implementations are really helpful for programmatic interfaces and frameworks. (+1) ● Another user commented "Protection from being used as training data for LLMs". Given recent results such as Google Gemini Pro being able to translate Kalamang in-context, as well as a human, with just a single book describing Kalamang grammar – I think we might want to consider that LLMs can be useful tools to enable preservation of such rare languages as well. We would not, for instance, want to blanket ban these uses as they will help us go further, with less. We might want to instead consider where we want to use them for research, and where we do not.

Outcome 2: Improve the description, discovery and reuse of language data

APPROACH	RESPONSES
Discovery and annotation of language materials in GLAM and other existing institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Needs to be a concerted effort to identify what languages are represented in collections (+1) ● "Needs to be a concerted effort to identify what languages are represented in collections" - Yes, as well as what connections already exist, and what they look like ● Can AI help in identifying , from metadata, what languages are represented in a catalogue entry? Or at least make a pretty good guess (+1) ● Use Nyingarn to expose manuscripts in a secure workspace in order to identify what languages and topics are in a manuscript (+2)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Are current metadata profiles specific enough, or are they lowest common denominator? ● "Are current metadata profiles specific enough, or are they lowest common denominator?" - and who creates the metadata in institutional catalogues - how good is the quality and consistency of this anyway? Cd there be a way of identifying all different metadata/tags used in a catalogue and systematising them? with some NLP techniques? ● Can be a very slow process. Using OCR and crowd sourced transcription can help speed it up. ● "Can be a very slow process. Using OCR and crowd sourced transcription can help speed it up." - This is what is provided in Nyingarn ● "Can be a very slow process. Using OCR and crowd sourced transcription can help speed it up." - how do you ensure the accuracy of crowd sourced data? ● Metadata is key for larger scale data and researchers will rely on this for statistical analysis especially. Thus the more universal and rigorously followed the data model the better. (+1) ● Improved policy framework relating to the data source / ownership? ● As a scoping activity, it could be useful to identify collections on a thematic basis rather than by library/institution (e.g. oral histories by X group; oral histories about X event) ● "As a scoping activity, it could be useful to identify collections on a thematic basis rather than by library/institution (e.g. oral histories by X group; oral histories about X event)" - Would be great to be able to search like this ● Partnerships with GLAM institutions: research collabs could be a win-win ● "Partnerships with GLAM institutions: research collabs could be a win-win" - some libraries have 'fellowship' options - perhaps that could be something to explore - example: https://www.sl.nsw.gov.au/about-library/fellowships ● linkage of datasets across different institutions (+1) ● Crowdsourcing identifying language content in catalogues, even using a standoff catalogue (or spreadsheet) to point to catalogues that do not allow contributions (+3) ● means to discover and explore datasets ● Discovery though a map is very intuitive and these language collections have a strong inherent spatial dimension (+2)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Would be great to have project funding for students (and speakers of the languages in the collections) and others get involved in helping to identify language that is missing metadata (+3) ● Opportunities to connect with other kinds of tools ● How to reach out, discover, and develop partnerships/interoperability with data/materials holders in other research disciplines? ● Fund Wiki language-a-thons, to add language metadata (+1) ● AI and automated tooling can automatically translate, transcribe, extract and annotate with metadata at scale, and produce concept and collection maps
Data Portals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide a range of UI access metaphors that and allow users to switch between them (+2) ● support map and node graph access metaphors (+2) ● good metadata accompanying the dataset (+1) ● Earmark funding for longevity/sustainability of portals (+2) ● good indexing for discovery of data (+2) ● Would be good to have a means for users to offer feedback, so portal can be altered to improve user experience ● it will be tricky to manage the the wide range of metadata and affordances of items in the portal, but this is also an incredible opportunity to provide a variety of ways to search and explore ● foreground the content as well as the metadata ● undertake user segmentation and design UX for different research use cases ● it should be clear where each item is held - is it stored in the LDACA portal, with another infrastructure provider, with a research group, in a community, or with individuals. Not only does this make it easier for people to see how each item will need to be worked with and who it is owned by / stored with, it will show off the rich variety within LDACA and make it clear the portal is just a window into data rather than a hoard of data. (+5) ● easy to understand user guides ● generous interfaces as UI options ● user-friendly interface (+3) ● Should the data portal allow users to preview the data (i.e. listen to audio, watch videos, read/view texts)? (+1) ● Portals should be built on standard API framework for flexibility and maintainability. UI should be loosely coupled to data. Monolithic systems are destined to fall out of date. (+2) ● "Portals should be built on standard API framework for flexibility and maintainability. UI should be loosely coupled to data. Monolithic

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<p>systems are destined to fall out of date. " - Good summary of the approach LDaCA is trying to take!</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use open-source non-proprietary applications as much as possible (+3) ● vocabularies and metadata schemas are important here (+6) ● Develop capability for researchers to tag assets with bespoke vocabularies to facilitate research projects. (+1) ● Develop a MyCollection capability to allow researchers to tag assets of interest into private thematic collections. (+2)
<p>Community-controlled workspaces for researchers and communities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● clear access control via knowledge of the hierarchy of approvers in the community (+1) ● Need ways to forge relationships between communities (researcher and language) to avoid wheel re-invention ● knowledge of cultural sensitivities that accompanies the data collection (+1) ● Need to be mindful of ways to bridge the digital divide (+2) ● Can community always be clearly identified? e.g. how do we deal with historical data with no clear contemporary cultural ownership? ● can these workspaces be used not only to collaborate but also discover potential collaborators? (+1) ● Invite non-technical people into technical communities and vice versa ● To be community and ability-inclusive, you need to be able to obtain and share context and description and even access and usage guidance in a variety of media - most especially audio, and video (+2) ● Also to be community enabled and appropriate, some metadata and usage guidance needs to be in the community's language, and also possibly in audio form. (+2) ● comments or feedback function to allow interactions and collaboration (+1) ● "comments or feedback function to allow interactions and collaboration " - this might be a good thing as an example of a (semi-)separate tool/interface to build on top of the portal - a forum that can link to / embed metadata, searches etc from the data portal, or a tool that adds commenting alongside the portal etc etc. ● Is it possible to develop a suite of solutions using (existing tools-Word press, Mukurtu etc) for this that a relatively cheap and easy for communities to implement? (+1) ● "Is it possible to develop a suite of solutions using (existing tools-Word press, Mukurtu etc) for this that a relatively cheap and easy for communities to implement?" - Yes, but with regular exports

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<p>to a common format for backup. LDACA's common format would be RO-Crate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "Is it possible to develop a suite of solutions using (existing tools-Word press, Mukurtu etc) for this that a relatively cheap and easy for communities to implement?" - Or a decision tree/grid for pros/cons of different solutions. ● Examples! Show examples of how other groups can build with / on top of / alongside LDACA. (+1) ● different workspace affordances for different kinds of document/text/community goals (including but also beyond language communities, eg re oral histories etc) (+1) ● Usage instructions & interfaces in multiple (community) languages ● "Usage instructions & interfaces in multiple (community) languages" - also for users with disabilities? ● Language communities need to be involved at the governance level and also in providing models that can be available for others to draw on. (+2) ● Build a community of practice for LDACA-extenders - a place where people building their own tools and workspaces that interact with LDACA components can talk to each other and share ideas, experiences, and support. This will also be an invaluable feedback pathway for LDACA improvement and a venue for partnership development. (+3)

Outcome 3: Increase user capability and confidence with LDaCA infrastructure

APPROACH	RESPONSES
<p>Building relationships with and capability in data custodians</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "Data custodians" needs expansion - in some Indigenous communities this concept can be complex and negotiated and changing in time, relevant parties can be clans, moieties, families, not just individuals and recognised organisations. (+3) ● ""Data custodians" needs expansion - in some Indigenous communities this concept can be complex and negotiated and changing in time..." - also relevant for non-Indigenous language communities, eg Deaf community - who should be the custodian/s? ● Since custodianship can be socially determined, and dynamic/negotiated, then currently the best model for enacting it is some kind of social networking model (+1) ● Research partnerships with GLAM institutions

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● clear responsibilities for data custodians (+1) ● Training in communities ● Have a facilitator or mentor for the custodians to check in with and vice versa. ● Research scholarships & bursaries for language community members (+2) ● Roadshows with workshops in communities with practical outcomes (scanning records, crowdsourced transcription, wikihacks) (+2) ● Conversations/ checklists to help people realise when they are data custodians would be useful (+1) ● Partnering with Regional language champions for Indigenous languages ● Use LDaCA language data as basis for small-module online language instruction -- see Evans-Mettouchi Dalabon videos ● Language communities members as CIs/PIs on language research projects (+1) ● Starting with training for students at all levels
Language and text analytics notebooks and tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● alternatives to notebooks? (+2) ● I want to echo some of the other comments in that while Jupyter notebooks are great – we develop some of them - there is a huge under-served base of researchers who are locked out from or hampered by such tools. We need simpler, cleaner ways to do basic analysis of these data and answer research questions without the barrier to entry that notebooks present. This requires work, but it is work worth doing! As is always the case in accessibility – helping those who cannot use notebooks to also get a handle on the data actually enables those who can to go further as well! ● We also need to do more to tap into existing tools rather than so much work-from-scratch. I feel that better UX on existing tools for a wider audience could be much more valuable here than new but hard to maintain tools with limited users. ● what text analytics tools and interfaces would community users find useful, those for whom APIs and notebooks are too much of a barrier. Simple, intuitive UI for selected text analytics that would be of interest to many/most?

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Only a limited proportion will be able/want to engage with APIs and Notebooks (+1) ● "Only a limited proportion will be able/want to engage with APIs and Notebooks" - Peer modelling may be useful here - seeing that someone at their "level" of techniness can use them and what for...rather than formal training use show n tell ● A common research paradigm is the semantic annotation of assets and the generation of a node graph. ● For language, think AUDIO FIRST, !!! (or video for sign languages users) ● "For language, think AUDIO FIRST, !!! (or video for sign languages users)" - LDaCA is not going to create a new ELAn or a new Praat ● "For language, think AUDIO FIRST, !!! (or video for sign languages users)" - "LDaCA is not going to create a new ELAn or a new Praat" - It's not only about "analysis" or annotation, it's about providing context, access, usage guidance etc. and being inclusive of both contribution and usage by e.g. Aboriginal languages speakers ● interoperability of tools ● Map-style navigation interfaces that allow a deep dive as well as broad "landscape" overview of the data are intuitive because many of us now use these interfaces in other contexts (+1) ● version control is an issue as notebooks are being improved based on user testing and feedback (+2) ● it would be great to get to a point where we can go beyond notebooks - there's a whole world out there of technical ways to enable analysis. Python/R packages, R Shiny interactives, Observable, modular software tools, visualisation utilities... Notebooks are wonderful, but it's limiting to only consider them. Not all utilities/activities are notebook shaped. (+1) ● "it would be great to get to a point where we can go beyond notebooks ..." - but also - if datasets can be downloaded (and converted into a range of formats), users could use them with other analysis tools as appropriate (Praat, ELAN etc) ● The capability of researchers to annotate assets with (private) custom terms and/or custom data would support a wide range or research propositions.

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● More chances to see each other's projects useful here - even tiny problems solved. Community of practice? ● Tapping into existing tools ● Notebooks are excellent at a dataset-experiment-result set research paradigm but this is only one paradigm and not even the most common. ● Provide UI for common research workflows. ● Remember, LDACA does not (and can not) provide all tools for all things. You should provide some, but focus on examples and documentation and enabling community-developed workspaces, tools, and interfaces. Otherwise you'll be trapped into doing all of the work yourself for all of the people. ● Yes! Great idea providing a safe space to upload some content, use a tool, get an output without the fear of wondering who else will have the data (+1) ● Technical docs and tools for intermediate skill levels *in addition to* beginner. ● recommendations for tools to use in workflow for research data collection and analysis ● Who will provide training for users?
<p>Training for data users in use of LDaCA infrastructure and tools</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● User experience of finding and accessing assets should be intuitive to the point that training is largely redundant. (+2) ● Short (3 min) videos showing basic interface for each tool would be helpful for people curious, stimulating further investigation (+2) ● "Short (3 min) videos showing basic interface for each tool would be helpful for people curious, stimulating further investigation" - Problem when tools are still being updated/changed - new videos would need to be created for each update ● workflows for management of collections by custodians can be made intuitive so they require minimal training and support ● "workflows for management of collections by custodians can be made intuitive so they require minimal training and support" - What is "Intuitive" to one person is confusing to another, and that is exacerbated by cultural differences. ● video tutorials ● train the trainers to scale up training

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Forums to ask researchers what training they want would be useful ● There are traps for the unwary in quantitative analysis of data so smaller modules could ideally be linked to coherent micro-courses and even to micro-credentials -- with recommended online courses. ● integration into some coursework ● data transformation requires specific skill sets and might not be effective to attempt to train researchers.. ● "data transformation requires specific skill sets and might not be effective to attempt to train researchers.." - Building workflows for preparing data for common tools can help. ● user guides; help pages (+1) ● "user guides; help pages" - for example, the guide written for the 50 words website: https://arts.unimelb.edu.au/data/assets/pdf_file/0005/3352838/50Words_A5ActivityBooklet-V3-.pdf ● FAQs ● Prepare exercises/ activities using the portal/data, that might appeal to different user groups (e.g. school students, researchers, community members) - gamify (+2) ● general awareness-raising of text analytics concepts ● hands-on training with supplementary materials before and after (+1) ● Training in communities (+1) ● data transformation including application of metadata would conventionally be done as a consultation with the data owner. Training seems an unlikely strategy in majority of circumstances ● concrete use cases for training (+1) ● Examples, examples, examples. ● leveraging events that are already happening ● CIs as champions, promoting the project/portal/tools - offering demos etc. at conferences, at universities, in communities (with local museums) (+3) ● useful case studies showcasing applications of tools on specific data collection to answer research questions (+3) ● integrating training in existing university courses (by Ldaca team or others) (+3)

APPROACH	RESPONSES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "integrating training in existing university courses (by Ldaca team or others)" - training / workshops / assessment ● Discussion forums, communities of practice, meetups, office hours - let the users of LDACA talk to and support each other. That way LDACA is a community not just some distant untouchable research resource. (+2) ● Echo all of the comments in this box!